

LIMNOLOGY AROUND (A MORE EXTREME) WORLD: GERMANY

Getting into hot water: The challenge of heatwaves for freshwater ecosystems

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The magnitude and frequency of extreme weather events (EWE) are increasing owing to anthropogenic climate change (Seneviratne *et al.* 2021, IPCC 2023), and with it, the urgency to understand their effects on biological communities. EWE are

Kirkpatrick & Lewis, 2020), meaning that they are becoming an intensifying stressor for communities. Our understanding of the degree to which EWE in general, and heatwaves in particular, affect communities is growing, but still needs to be improved.

Freshwaters are among the most vulnerable to heatwaves (Tassone *et al.*, 2023; Woolway *et al.*, 2021). Freshwater ecosystems are among the most threatened ecosystems worldwide because drainage basins accumulate the effects of multiple stressors in the large landscapes they connect to (Reid *et al.*, 2019). In addition, they hold a disproportionate diversity compared to the area they cover, although a high proportion of that diversity is currently threatened (Tickner *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, many aquatic organisms are ectotherms, making them particularly vulnerable to temperature changes (Bonacina *et al.*, 2023). Water temperature strongly influences metabolic rates, species interactions and distributions, and ecosystem productivity. Therefore, the ecological consequences of increasing temperatures likely include local extinctions of sensitive species (Biswas & Mallik, 2011), compositional changes (Cortés-Guzmán *et al.*, 2024), and the introduction of non-native species (Gu *et al.*, 2023), ultimately disrupting ecosystem processes, functions, and services (Capon *et al.*, 2021). Moreover, the short duration, unpredictability, and high intensity of heatwaves can rapidly exceed the thermal limits of many organisms and affect communities more strongly than moderate and gradual changes in temperature (Jentsch *et al.*, 2007).

Heatwaves represent a complex challenge for freshwater communities. They must cope with heatwaves while being under the effects of multiple anthropogenic stressors. Anthropogenic

Fig. 1 Spatial (a) and temporal (b) distributions of heatwaves across European rivers. Intensity was measured as the excess heat in three consecutive days, exceeding 90% of the annual temperature distribution. Modified figure from Cortés-Guzmán *et al.* 2024.

discrete in time, rare in probability (e.g. <5% or <1% of occurrence based on climatic records), and frequently have deleterious effects on communities and ecosystems (Sabater *et al.*, 2022; Smith, 2011). Among EWE, heatwaves have increased worldwide in intensity, frequency, and duration since the 1950s (Perkins-

stressors, including heatwaves, vary in intensity in space and time (Fig. 1; Blowes *et al.*, 2019). Research aimed at understanding the effects of heatwaves should include their spatiotemporal variation and their interaction with other stressors (Jackson *et al.*, 2021). For example, in a previous study, we addressed the

effects of heatwaves by decomposing their temporal and spatial variations and found that sites undergoing heatwaves of higher intensity showed lower taxonomic and functional diversity than sites experiencing lower-magnitude heatwaves (Fig 2a, 2b; Cortés-Guzmán *et al.*, 2024). We also analysed the interaction of heatwaves with the ecological quality of the community and land cover. We found that communities with better ecological quality and in forested areas were highly sensitive to heatwaves (Fig. 2c-f), likely related to a higher proportion of sensitive species being lost after heatwaves of high magnitude. Other studies have analysed the interaction of heatwaves with pollutants (Hermann *et al.*, 2023; Wang *et al.*, 2023) and found that the combination of both modified the community composition and trophic structure. However, the interaction effects varied greatly among study groups and from individuals to communities (Polazzo *et al.*, 2022). It is clear from these studies that there are many more factors to consider. For example, the synergistic or antagonistic effects of other extreme events, such as floods or droughts, and the degree of synchronisation between disturbances (Jackson *et al.*, 2021) are open and promising research fields that will contribute to our understanding of the effects of global change on freshwater biodiversity.

To address the complexity of stressors, we need to add complexity to biological responses. Community responses vary spatially and temporally; therefore, communities usually do not cope with disturbances in a synchronised manner (Jackson *et al.*, 2021; Palmer *et al.*, 2017). The variation in responses depends on the range of species functional traits (Ross *et al.*, 2022), connectivity

higher mortality than an event occurring during the adult stage, when individuals can migrate over longer distances (Cinto Mejía & Wetzel, 2023). However, if heatwaves affect individuals during their reproductive stage, the population might not recover in the long term (Kingsolver & Buckley, 2017). Integrating traits, lags, and synchrony in aquatic community responses is an important venue that will increase our knowledge of the effects of heatwaves and other extreme events.

Our ability to predict the effects of heatwaves determines our ability to mitigate them. By understanding where and when communities are more vulnerable to heatwaves, decision makers and stakeholders can direct conservation efforts efficiently. Although simultaneously addressing multiple stressors increases the complexity of community responses, these interactions can also be used in our favour. For example, conservation actions aimed at mitigating the effects of warmer temperatures, such as maintaining or restoring riparian forests, also mitigate the effects of pollutants, which can make communities generally more resistant to heatwaves. Mitigating the effects of global change on freshwater communities is of paramount importance because adverse consequences for ecosystem services are anticipated owing to shifts in their composition and function (Capon *et al.*, 2021). For example, provisioning services, such as food resources from cold-adapted species like salmonids, are threatened by warming and heatwaves (Almodóvar *et al.*, 2012). In addition, water security is also threatened by heatwaves, which deteriorate the quantity and quality of water (Graham *et al.*, 2024; Van Vliet *et al.*, 2023) for aquatic communities and humans. The complex dynamics between heatwaves, community resilience, and ecosystem services demand further research to uncover innovative conservation strategies that not only mitigate these risks, but also enhance our capacity to adapt to an increasingly changing climate.

Fig. 2 Responses of river invertebrate communities to heatwaves. Taxon richness (a, c, e) and functional richness (b, d, f) decreased in sites exposed to high-intensity heatwaves. The intensity of the heatwaves was measured as the excess heat in three consecutive days, exceeding 90% of the annual temperature distribution. The upper panels (a, b) show the community response to increasing heatwave intensity. The middle panels (c and d) show the community response to the heatwave intensity interacting with the ecological quality of the community. The lower panels (e, f) show the community response to heatwave intensity interacting with the proportion of forested areas upstream. For details, please refer to the original publication (Cortés-Guzmán *et al.* 2024).

to and diversity of the regional pool (Vad *et al.*, 2023), and community ecological memory, which is the influence of past stressors on future responses (Jackson *et al.*, 2021). For example, communities in warmer regions might be composed of more warm-tolerant species but might be closer to their thermal limits than communities in colder regions (Cortés-Guzmán *et al.*, 2024; Maxwell *et al.*, 2019). On the other hand, temporal variation is often related to the time lag in community responses (Essl *et al.*, 2015) and when the event occurs during community assembly (Cinto Mejía & Wetzel, 2023). For example, an event occurring during the larval development of aquatic insects might result in

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